

Religious Orientation, Social Dominance and Existential Insecurity in Older Adults of Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 27, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Religious Orientation, Social Dominance, Existential Insecurity, Older Adults</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6321220</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to investigate the relationship between Religious Orientation, Social Dominance and Existential Insecurity in Older Adults. In this regard, a review of available literature was done critically, and a method consisted of quantitative research was used. Correlational design was used in this research. A sample consisted of 200 participants was obtained with the help of purposive sampling, and their age range was 40-60 years. Standardized questionnaires were used to collect the data. Correlation analysis, t-test and moderation through AMOS was used. It was revealed that there is a significant relationship between Religious Orientation, Social Dominance and Existential Insecurity in Older Adults. Social dominance moderates the relationship between religious orientation and existential insecurity in older adults. Moreover, it was identified that there is no significant difference in religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity in terms of family system among older adults. On the basis of discussion, it was suggested that there is a need for further studies on the topic. Lastly, the strengths, limitations, and future implication of the study were highlighted. The study will help in understanding the issues faced by older adults, and how religiosity is experienced in older adulthood.</i></p>

Introduction

Religion is playing a key role in the lives of most human beings, particularly the older, as it manages the most of the mechanism of life for them. Furthermore, in the life of depressed and anxious older persons, it plays an arbitrate role (Cheong, Huang, & Poon, 2011). This is the reason that, there is the large number of aged persons, those prefer to have some religion to get rid of anxiety and depression. On the other hand, social dominance occurs when members of a social group vary in their ability to get hold of other participants (i.e. compete). Outdated strategies of social dominance frequently emphasize authoritarian behaviour, but nonetheless indicate that the main figures (e.g. seen, desirable social partners) are socially important. Furthermore, these trends only occur up to a certain age for men (Allport, 1967). The idea is that in places where such a feeling is not present, it is now my argument that it is indeed useful to examine the relationship entre, on one hand, existential insecurity (and often associated with existential insecurity-uncertainty and questions over its very life and identity) and, on the other, religiosity. However, it's not true, as Allport(1967) actually suggests, to reserve the feelings of existential vulnerability for people from poor nations and poor regions. If religiousness is only related to poverty in poor nations, we could not "explain" why the USA is a religious nation or why so many rich people in the western world are religious people (it is well known that in Britain, for example, New Age be it public worship or consumer worship hire its members white (Allport, 1967).

Religious activities pose an even harder puzzle. Including religions, many of the non-religious activities that individuals choose to do contribute to the rules of eating, drinking, sexual immorality, caring for children, building social connections, etc. Adaptations can be seen of the psychological mechanisms that underlie these behaviors. Some things are not also evident, such as music and art, but often recognized as by-products of change (Pargament, 2002).

The role of spirituality and religion in mental health has fascinated researchers in the last 40 years (Pargament, 2002). Religious beliefs or people's reasons for faith are of particular interest. Allport and Ross (1967) theorized that there are four kinds of religious orientation: fundamental, religiose, outside, non-religious and non-religious. Those with an intrinsic religious outlook live their religion and search through their religion for meaning and value. Individuals whose religion is socially focused use their faith rather than their religion, and may participate for purposes of community or family. Those who are indiscriminately religious respond in a positive manner to any question perceived to be religious on the scale of religious orientation (ROS), and those who are not religious or non-religious indiscriminately answer religious questions in an adverse manner (Allport & Ross, 1967).

Religious and mental comfort have been connected so far. Researches have been conducted to find out their beginning point to see to how much degree the intellectual satisfaction finds its way deep to religion. It is furthermore suggested that religious belief provided comfort, peace and solace to inner self. The aim of this study has been to dissolve the issue of whether having spiritual belief can be fruitful in solving the effects of eating and this can pave way for its treatment also. During the era of last 40 years, many works have been carried out to find a better understanding of mental comfort in relation with spiritual health (Allport & Ross, 1967; Pargament, 2002).

The motivation of religious behaviour is known as the motivation (Hoge, 1972). The explanation for religious behaviour is religious orientation (Francis, 2007). Religious orientation, a religious belief or dogma is distinct from the abstract religious orientation and meaningless (Aronson, et al., 1998). For Allport, it was rather the pureness of motive that was important to have a religious belief, even its orthodoxy. Persons in their religious orientation may be inherent or foreign. Allport and Ross (1967) defined the religious orientation as inherent in this orientation: "Persons who have that orientation are motivated by religion. The other needs are seen as less alternative and, as far as possible, harmonize with religious beliefs and laws. Other needs are seen to be as strong as possible. After embracing a creed, everyone tries to internalize it and follow it completely. Allport and Ross (1967) have defined a religious orientation: 'Persons who have this approach are prepared to use religion for their own purposes. In this sense he lives his religion.' (Allport & Ross, 1967). The concept is borrowed from axiology to suggest a holding interest because it represents the overall interests of others. Foreign values are always instrumental and useful.

People with this orientation can find religion useful for providing security and consolation, sociability and distraction, status and self-justification in different ways. The embraced creed is lightly held or else selectively shaped to fit more primary needs. In the theological terms the extrinsic type turns to God, but without turning away from self." (Allport & Ross, 1967). The problem of the religious instruction of its members is an important issue in view of the important role of the Greek Orthodox Church in preserving the Greek ethnic identity while researching its orientation to receive psychological help. Nevertheless, this does not mean that a member of the Greek Orthodox Church is only a matter of maintaining ethnic and cultural identity. People who are members of the Greek Orthodox Church for purely religious reasons are in fact involved in a deep faith in Jesus Christi expressed in the Greek Orthodox Church, by preserving culture or by social recognition.

The research shows that people "who are religious" under various criteria appear to be more prejudicial than people who are not "religious" (Wilson, 1960) is of interest in this analysis of literature. His studies focused on several experiments which indicated this hypothesis. The ERV scales and the instruments measuring religious conventionalism were used. The ERV scale was used. ERV is a scale, used to measure antisemitism to determine the quantity of prejudice of the sample. The ERV assessed the extent to which every person is extrinsically religious or the degree of unconscious or self-serving roles for a participant's religion. This can be seen how a person "uses his or her faith". The opposite is intrinsic religiosity, which is that a person "vies his faith" as a single end, and most individuals fall into the continuum (Aronson, et al., 1998).

The results showed a high correlation between ERV and antisemitism generally, indicating a high connection between religiosity and antisemitism. Research in Wilson, as well as previous research like that, has shown that church employees are more influenced than non-churchgoers and people with an extrinsic religious orientation than individuals with more intrinsic religious orientation (Allport & Kramer, 1946; Rokeach, 1960). From these findings, an important cause for the creation of a tolerant or prejudicial life outlook is the inner experience of faith, which implies to the person (Allport & Ross, 1967). Allport and Ross (1967) tried to discover whether a certain type of cognitive style penetrated many people's thinking in a way that was indiscriminately pro-religious and, in addition, highly prejudiced. The questionnaire, which includes negative statements about African Americans, Jews, Muslims, Mexican and Puerto Ricans, was used as part of the study. The second set of measures consisted of the indirect prejudice scale, which includes various declarations about psychotropic diseases and the philosophy of life in the jungle, which subjects might agree or disagree with. The final measure was the measure of religious orientation, which involves objects measuring both intrinsic and extrinsic religiosity (Aronson, et al., 1998).

The leading objectives of the current study are to assess the relationship between religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity among elderly population. Further, it also aimed to study the role of religious orientation in connection to social dominance. It is thought that religious orientation act as buffer to reduce the negative effects of existential insecurity, to find out the moderating role of social dominance between religious orientation and existential insecurity.

In this regard, the proposed hypotheses are:

H1: There is likely to be a significant relationship between existential insecurity and social dominance in older adults.

H2: There is likely to be significant relationship between existential insecurity and religious orientation in older adults.

H3 Social dominance is likely to moderate the relationship between religious orientation and existential insecurity in older adults.

H4: There is likely to be significant differences in family system in terms of social dominance, religious orientation and existential insecurity.

Method

The research uses positivism as the core paradigm, because the aim was to verify the evidences on the basis of science. Correlational research design was used to find out relationship between religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity. The sample of this study was 200, with an age range of 40-60 years, and it was calculated through G-Power Analysis. Purposive Sampling technique was used to collect the data. The standardized tools that were used in this regard include Demographic Information Sheet, Existential Security Scale (Loster & Khaleq, 2003), Social Dominance Orientation Scale (Sidanius, Pratto, & Mitchell, 1994) and Religious Orientation Scale (Khodadady & Bagheri, 2005). The analyses that were used to make statistical inferences included Descriptive statistics, Reliability analysis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Moderation analysis (AMOS) and t-test for independent sample. All ethical considerations were followed in this research.

Results and Discussion

The aim of this study was to assess the relationship between religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity in older adults. The data was collected from participants using standardized questionnaires, and after entering the data into sheets, descriptive statistics were executed to obtain frequencies, and percentage of the demographic variables, to verify if the standardized scales are measuring the variables in given population, reliability test was used. Moreover, in order to identify a correlation between religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity in older adults, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used. t-test for independent sample was used to see if there is a difference in social dominance, religious orientation and existential insecurity in terms of family system. Moderation analysis was conducted to see the moderating role of social dominance. The obtained results can be seen in the tabulated form:

Table 3.1
Psychometric properties of Questionnaires

Variable	k	M (SD)	Range		Skew	α
			Actual	Potential		
Religious Orientation	40	110.17 (13.56)	52-173	5-30	-.706	.80
Religious Orientation Intrinsic	6	17.6 (2.63)	4-20	5-20	-.044	.76
Religious Orientation Social	4	24.31 (4.20)	6-30	6-30	.800	.72
Religious Orientation Concessional	4	17.90 (5.41)	9-25	5-25	-2.558	.66
Religious Orientation Theo-Pacific	3	21.47 (2.95)	8-25	5-25	-1.326	.61
Religious Orientation Humanitarian	2	19.55 (3.16)	5-25	5-25	-1.962	.72
Religious Orientation Sacrificial	4	9.33 (1.09)	2-9	2-10	.167	.64
Social Dominance	20	75.46 (7.62)	52-99	16-112	-.862	.63
Existential Insecurity	6	14.23 (5.02)	6-30	6-30	-2.315	.74

Note. k= Constant, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, α = Cronbach's Alpha

From table, it can be seen that Religious Orientation scale has high reliability as Cronbach's α .80. The total items are 40, and the mean score is 110.17 ($SD = 13.56$). The Cronbach's α for Religious Orientation Intrinsic (subscale) is .76, which is high. The items are 6, mean is 17.6 ($SD = 2.63$). Another subscale, Religious Orientation Social has the Cronbach's α .72, which is moderate. The items are 4, and the mean score is 24.31 ($SD = 4.20$). The Religious Orientation Concessional subscale has Cronbach's α .66, which is moderate. The items are 4 and mean score is 17.90 ($SD = 5.41$). The Religious Orientation Theo-Pacific scale has Cronbach's α .61, which is moderate. The test items are 3, and the mean score is 21.47 ($SD = 2.95$). The Religious Orientation Humanitarian scale has Cronbach's α .72, which is moderate. The items are 2, and the mean score is 19.55 ($SD = 3.16$). The Religious Orientation Sacrificial scale has Cronbach's α .64. The items are 4, and the mean score is 9.33 ($SD = 1.09$). The Social Dominance scale has Cronbach's α .63. The items are 20 and the mean score is 75.46 ($SD = 7.62$). The Existential Insecurity scale has Cronbach's α .74, which is moderate. The items are 6, and the mean score is 14.23 ($SD = 5.02$).

Table 3.2

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	M	SD
1. Religious Orientation Scale	-	.65**	.81**	.65**	.75**	.71**	.43**	.04	.015	1.10	13.56

2.	Religious Orientation-Intrinsic Scale	-	.57**	.08	.68**	.33**	.28**	.34**	-.13	17.61	2.63
3.	Religious Orientation - Social Scale		-	.32**	.58**	.46**	.32**	.06	.50	24.31	4.20
4.	Religious Orientation-Concessional Scale			-	.21**	.34**	.15	-.22**	.11**	17.91	5.41
5.	Religious Orientation Theo-pacific Scale				-	.502**	.35**	.25**	-.037	21.47	2.95
6.	Religious Orientation-Humanitarian Scale					-	.35**	-.07	.02	19.55	3.16
7.	Religious Orientation-Sacrificial Scale						-	.06	-.21**	9.33	1.09
8.	Social Dominance Scale							-	-.12	75.47	7.62
9.	Existential Insecurity Scale								-	14.23	5.02

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis between study variables
*Note: p<.001**, p<.01**, p<.05* M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation*

Table indicated that there is a relationship between religious orientation and social dominance ($r=.04$, $p<.05$). Table also indicated that there is a relationship between religious orientation and existential insecurity ($r=.02$, $p<.05$).

Table 3.3
Sample descriptive using t-test for equality of means

Variables	Individual	Collective	t	p	95 % CI	
	M (SD)	M (SD)			LL	UL
Religious Orientation	110.23 (13.49)	110.11 (13.70)	.62	.952	-3.57	3.91
Social Dominance	76.21 (7.78)	74.72 (7.42)	1.38	.243	-.62	3.60
Existential Insecurity	14.62 (5.03)	13.84 (5.00)	1.11	.823	-.61	2.17

From the table 3.3, it can be seen that the t-test was used to identify the differences in religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity in terms of family system. It was found that there is no significant difference between the collective and individual family systems with regard to religious orientation, social dominance and existential insecurity.

Table 3.4
Conditional Effect of X on Y at the Values of Moderator (s)

Relationship	Low /High SD	β	S.E	t	p
RO-->EI	Low	.01	.03	.36	.71
	High	-.17	.04	-1.94	.043

Note: EI = Existential Insecurity. RO = Religious Orientation. SD = Social Dominance.

Results indicate significant interaction effect of religious orientation x social dominance ($\beta = -1.73, p = .009$). On comparing the values of effects (i.e. β is -0.17 for high social dominance and $.01$ for low social dominance) and examining respective p values it can be seen that hypothesis is supported.

Figure 3.1

The first hypothesis, aimed to identify the relationship between existential insecurity and social dominance. It can be seen from the correlation analysis that the study is supported by limited previous literature. There can be different reasons for the relationship between existential insecurity and social dominance (Islam, 2010). On the basis of theory of neoliberalism, which presents the idea of free trades and free will, along with independent. It was seen that neoliberalism is considered to be more correlated with social dominance and existential insecurity. A study that was done by Hale, (2005), aimed to present the idea that neoliberalism has been a new face for social and racial dominance in adults, because they aim to investigate the solution to their existing problems in the latest mind set.

Furthermore, the second hypothesis of the study was formulated to find a relationship between existential insecurity and religious orientation in older adults. It can be seen from the correlational analysis that the study is supported by the literature. People face different issues while ageing that often make them more reliant on the religious thoughts and practices. Sometimes it is due to their regrets, or terms with their offspring that make them feel depression and often other mental health issues in later life. Therefore, various studies assess that religious orientation changes with the increasing age. It has also been observed in the research that there is a positive relationship between religious practices and increasing age (Rowell, 1974).

However, it is unclear if existential insecurity negatively impacts religious orientation or not, because a mixed literature is available on the given topic. There have been different region-based studies that present the negative relationship between religious orientation and existential insecurity, because the American population is more educated than Pakistani population. Moreover, due to the differences in demographic variables, a persons' religious perception might differ (Radzi, et al., 2014). Therefore, it can be said that further indigenous studies are required to make a clear statement on the relationship between religious orientation and existential insecurity.

The fourth hypothesis aimed to investigate the differences in social dominance, religious orientation and existential insecurity in terms of family system. It is revealed that the study did not found any such results. As collective family system is being replaced by separate or nuclear family system, the thinking patterns related to religion are also changing in population. At one hand, new generation living in nuclear family system are less likely to follow religion in western nations, it seems to be unlikely for eastern populations, because the concept of religiosity is being changed (Salfate et al., 2018). Similar findings are presented for the adult population as well. Therefore, it can be said that religious orientation is not based on the family system, rather it is more impacted by the social factors.

On the other hand, family system is also not linked with social dominance, as presented by the results of the study, because the result verified that there is no difference in social dominance with regard to family system. One of the contributing factors is identified as immigration, because the family that emigrated from one place to another and being nuclear were known to be linked with altered concept of social dominance (Shechory, & David, 2012). On the other hand, a research gap is exists with regard to collective family systems, which again highlights the need for future indigenous researches.

Conclusion

To conclude, it can be said that there is a relationship between existential insecurity, religious orientation and social dominance in older adults. Moreover, there are no differences in social dominance, religious orientation and existential insecurity in terms of family system. Social dominance moderates the relationship between religious orientation and existential insecurity in older adults. Limited extent of indigenous studies is available

on the given topic. This research can be proved quite useful for families as well as healthcare institutions as they are involved in dealing with community or caring for aging family members.

Recommendations

It can be highlighted that, as the topic is subject to social and religious differences, it is highly likeable to conduct more indigenous studies on the topic. Ensuring body health is not enough since sound mind can lead to sound body for which different applications can be studied. This will also help in highlighting the importance of mental health in older adults. Further, qualitative researches must be conducted on this topic in future.

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References

- Allport, G.W. and Ross, J.M., 1967. Personal religious orientation and prejudice. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 5(4), p.432.
- Aronson, Joshua, Quinn, Diane M., & Spencer, Steven J. (1998). Stereotype threat and the academic underperformance of minorities and women. In *Swim, J.K. & Stangor, C. (Eds.), Prejudice: The target's perspective*. San Diego, CA: Academic Press, pp. 83–103.
- Cheong, P. H., Huang, S., & Poon, J. P. (2011). Religious communication and epistemic authority of leaders in wired faith organizations. *Journal of Communication*, 61(5), 938-958.
- Hale, C. R. (2005). Neoliberal multiculturalism: the remaking of cultural rights and racial dominance in Central America. *Polar*, 28, 10.
- Hoge, R. (1972). A validated intrinsic religious motivation scale. *Journal for the scientific study of religion*, 369-376.
- Kepel, G., & Ghazaleh, P. (2004). *The war for Muslim minds: Islam and the West* (p. 256). Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Khodadady, E., & Bagheri, N. (2014). Development and validation of an Islamic religious orientation scale with pilgrims of Imam Reza shrine. *Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 3(8), 37-50.
- Lester, D., & Francis, L. J. (1993). Is religiosity related to suicidal ideation after personality and mood are taken into account?. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 15(5), 591-592.
- Pargament, K. I. (1997). *The psychology of religion* and Guilford Press.
- Pargament, K. I. (2002). The bitter and the sweet: An evaluation of the costs and benefits of religiousness. *Psychological inquiry*, 13(3), 168-181.
- Radzi, H. M., Ramly, L. Z., Ghazali, F., Sipon, S., & Othman, K. (2014). Religious and spiritual coping used by student in dealing with stress and anxiety. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 4(2), 314-319.
- Rokeach, M. (1960). *The open and closed mind: Investigations into the nature of belief systems and personality systems*.
- Rowell, T. E. (1974). The concept of social dominance. *Behavioral biology*, 11(2), 131-154.
- Salfate, Salvador & Páez, Darío & Liu, James & Pratto, Felicia & Gil de Zúñiga, Homero.(2018). A Comparison of Social Dominance Theory and System Justification: The Role of Social Status in 19 Nations. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*. 44. 10.1177/0146167218757455.
- Shechory, M., & David, S. B. (2012). Social dominance, family system and deviance among immigrant youth in Israel. *Minority groups: Coercion, discrimination, exclusion, deviance and the quest for equality*. New York: nova Science Publishers, Inc, 247-263.
- Sidanius, J., & Pratto, F. (2001). *Social dominance: An intergroup theory of social hierarchy and oppression*. Cambridge University Press.

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